

Experience of Foreign Countries in the Economic Development of Industry and Ways to Effectively Use it in the Conditions of Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT: This article systematically analyzes the experience of foreign countries in the economic development of industry, revealing their institutional, structural, and economic mechanisms. On this basis, conceptual ways of effective use of this experience in the conditions of Uzbekistan are substantiated, and an author's approach aimed at improving national industrial policy is proposed..

KEYWORDS: industry, industrial production, industry, investments, economic development, foreign experience.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern global economic space, industrial sectors play a decisive role in the sustainable growth of the national economy, increasing export potential, and accelerating technological progress. In particular, the intensification of competition on a global scale, the rapid change in the structure of industry, and the processes of transition to a "green" and digital economy make the issue of economic development of industry one of the priorities of state policy. From this point of view, the analysis of best practices in the development of industry in foreign countries and their use in accordance with national conditions is of current scientific and practical importance.

The experience of developed and newly industrialized countries shows that the economic development of industry is not limited to increasing production volumes, but is carried out through structural balance between industries, support for industries that create high added value, and expansion of investments in innovation and human capital. This approach serves to increase the industry's resistance to external shocks, increase labor productivity, and ensure a balance in the economic development of the regions.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the issue of economic development of industry is closely related to the diversification of the national economy, reducing dependence on raw materials, and the formation of modern industries. At the same time, it is important not to directly transfer the experience of foreign countries, but to adapt it, taking into account the institutional environment, resource potential, demographic factors, and regional characteristics.

In particular, the experience of developed and newly industrialized countries shows that the economic development of industry relies on long-term strategic planning, cooperation between the state and the private sector, as well as targeted support for industries that create high added value. However, these experiments yield different results depending on the economic structure, institutional environment, and resource capabilities of each country. Therefore, it is important not to accept foreign models as a universal solution, but to develop mechanisms for their adaptation to national conditions.

From this point of view, the study of the experience of foreign countries in the economic development of industry and ways of their effective use in the conditions of Uzbekistan is of great importance not only theoretically, but also practically. This issue serves as an important scientific and practical basis for improving national industrial policy, increasing investment activity, and ensuring sustainable economic growth.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Structural changes in the economy are manifested, first of all, through the formation of new forms and directions of economic activity. Such changes do not occur spontaneously, but require the creation of new spheres, their institutional support, and

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development based on practical experience. Foreign experience plays an important role in the formation of sustainable sources of economic growth, especially in the context of developing countries.

From this point of view, the development of effective models of socio-economic development, in particular, issues of increasing efficiency in the industrial sector, requires a deep analysis of the experience of developed foreign countries [1]. As practice shows, the results achieved in the economic development of industry are largely determined by the targeted selection of priority sectors and the consistency of long-term and short-term economic policies aimed at supporting these sectors. In this case, increasing competitiveness, introducing innovative solutions, and strengthening intersectoral integration are important factors [2].

In our opinion, in the economic development of industry, it is crucial not only to determine priority sectors, but also to effectively use available resources and opportunities, their optimal distribution, and direct financial flows towards specific goals. At the same time, the formation of a result-oriented management system and strengthening interaction between the state and the private sector are an important condition for the sustainable development of industries and achieving overall economic efficiency.

The experience of a developed country in this area shows, in particular:

The high economic efficiency of US industries is explained not by random factors, but by the combination of several closely interconnected priority advantages. In particular, the formation of a competitive environment in the production sphere, the high potential for the creation and implementation of innovative solutions, and human capital, relying on a knowledgeable and effective workforce, are the main drivers of industrial development. The systematic combination of these factors allows US industry to ensure long-term stability, maintain technological leadership, and successfully compete in global markets [3].

The German economy is characterized by the diversification of industrial sectors and deep institutional formation. Stable connections between production sectors and technological specialization in the country demonstrate Germany as a leading state with a strong industrial base on a European scale. In particular, the production of chemical products, the manufacture of industrial equipment and technological equipment, as well as the high development of machine-building industries, indicate the priority importance of industry in the national economy [4]. The interconnected functioning of these sectors is one of the main factors ensuring the competitiveness and export potential of the German economy.

Another important aspect of the German industrial model is the systematic formation of the necessary infrastructure for the stable and efficient functioning of production sectors. In particular, functional cooperation and mutual integration between industrial enterprises and service providers have been established at a high level, which ensures the continuity and efficiency of production processes [5].

At the same time, in the German experience, the economic impact of industry is not limited only to the value added directly created. Indirect economic results arising from mutual purchases between industrial enterprises and the service sector, logistics, maintenance, and consulting services are also taken into account comprehensively. As a result, this complex of interconnected industries accounts for an average of 8-9 percent of the country's gross economic product. This indicator is relatively high compared to other large economies of the European Union, clearly demonstrating the systemic and integrated nature of the German industrial model [6].

It is in this direction that Germany occupies a leading position on a global scale. In this practice, only the experience of Japan can be cited at a similar level. In other economically developed countries, this indicator is significantly lower than the level of Germany. In particular, in France this share is about two times less, while in Great Britain it is about 40 percent.

Such differences are explained, on the one hand, by differences in the structural composition of the economies of countries, and on the other hand, by the level of development of the infrastructure of scientific and applied research in industry and related industries, as well as the targeted implementation of strategic directions from the first stage [7]. These factors ensure the long-term effectiveness of the German economic model.

Export activity has a special priority in the German economic development strategy. A significant part of the products manufactured in the country is directed to foreign markets, and the share of exports is very high. At the same time, the predominance of industrial products in the structure of exported goods further strengthens the competitiveness of German industry in world markets. In these indicators, only Japan and Italy can compete with Germany to a certain extent.

Significantly, German industrial products occupy a stable position in world markets, accounting for a significant portion of the country's total exports. The effective organization of the export system and the high level of integration into foreign markets serve to increase Germany's investment attractiveness and create favorable conditions for attracting foreign capital to the national economy.

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the methods of induction and deduction were used in the process, general conclusions were formed based on the experience of individual countries, and practical proposals for the development of Uzbekistan's industry were developed based on general laws. The interdependence of industrial sectors, infrastructure, the investment climate, innovation activity, and state policy was also comprehensively considered through a systematic approach.

National and international official statistical data, state programs and strategic documents, reports of international organizations, and research results published in scientific publications were used as an information-empirical base. The obtained data were processed using generalization, grouping, and logical analysis methods, ensuring the scientific validity of the research conclusions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Among the experience of foreign countries, the Chinese industrial development model occupies a special place. The country is a world leader in terms of production volumes, and it accounts for a large part of industrial goods. Chinese industry is acquiring global significance not only in the production of traditional heavy industrial products, but also in the production of high-tech goods - vehicles, machinery and equipment, electronic devices, and infrastructure facilities. This reflects the multifaceted and comprehensive nature of the country's industry.

At the same time, the high share of heavy industry in China's industrial structure has led to a sharp increase in demand for energy and natural resources. The significant proportion of energy and electricity consumption in production processes contributes to the growth of intermediate consumption within the economy. This situation has necessitated financial support from the state for resource-supplying enterprises and companies engaged in the processing of carbon emissions, thereby shaping a distinct direction of industrial policy [8].

One of the key advantages of China's industrial efficiency lies in the strong emphasis placed on technical efficiency in production processes. In this context, systematic measures are implemented to ensure the full utilization of existing production capacities, that is, to reduce the gap between actual output and potential production capacity. In achieving technical efficiency, factors such as ownership structure, investment flows, the institutional environment, and research and development activities play a significant role [9].

At the same time, China's experience demonstrates that improving efficiency in industrial enterprises is not limited solely to technological advancement and capital investment. In certain cases, the scale of labor resources and the intensity of workforce utilization also have a significant impact on production outcomes. In this context, research and development activities carried out directly at the enterprise level - rather than by the state - exert a stronger influence on industrial efficiency and simultaneously stimulate regional technological development.

Another important feature of China's industrial model is its management approach focused on the efficient use of resources. At the enterprise level, the productivity of labor, capital, and other production factors is continuously analyzed, ensuring their optimal allocation. As a result, production costs are reduced and overall economic performance is enhanced.

In addition, the relatively high share of enterprises operating with foreign investment participation strengthens the competitive environment within the industrial sector and contributes to efficiency gains. Such enterprises, driven by profit-maximization objectives, promote technological upgrading and improvements in management quality.

At the current stage, digital transformation and the implementation of "Industry 4.0" principles have become priority areas of China's industrial policy. Through the adoption of advanced technologies, technical modernization, and the use of energy-efficient solutions, consistent measures are being implemented to enhance industrial production performance. In this regard, China's experience represents an important benchmark shaping global industrial development trends, alongside advanced economies such as the United States, Germany, and Japan.

In recent years, Russia has implemented systematic reforms aimed at increasing the share of industry - particularly manufacturing - within the structure of the national economy. Within this framework, expanding the number of enterprises introducing technological innovations, significantly increasing the volume of investment directed toward industry, and rapidly improving labor productivity have been identified as key priorities [10]. This approach not only supports the sustainable growth of industrial sectors but also strengthens the technological foundation of the national economy.

In particular, the introduction of a unified digital platform designed to ensure digital interaction between government authorities and industrial enterprises across different regions of the country has emerged as a significant institutional step. Through this platform, data on enterprise activities are systematically collected and analyzed using artificial intelligence

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technologies. This enables the assessment of the effectiveness of state support mechanisms, facilitates targeted decision-making, and enhances the overall effectiveness of industrial policy.

In our view, one of the most significant features of Russia's industrial policy is that reforms aimed at developing the manufacturing sector are grounded in the concept of "technological sovereignty". This approach seeks to reduce external technological dependence in strategic industrial sectors by relying on domestic production capabilities and national scientific and technological potential, thereby achieving long-term competitiveness. Alongside the utilization of foreign experience, this approach may also be regarded as an important methodological lesson for industrial economic development under the conditions of Uzbekistan.

The development of Kazakhstan's economy, particularly its industrial sector, is driven not only by the availability of abundant natural resources but also by the establishment of a favorable and open environment for economic activity. Measures aimed at encouraging entrepreneurship, ensuring the free functioning of market mechanisms, and reducing institutional barriers have emerged as key factors supporting industrial development. Such an approach has enabled Kazakhstan to achieve relatively high positions in international business environment rankings [11].

In recent years, Kazakhstan has implemented systematic reforms to support entrepreneurial activity, including the simplification of procedures for obtaining construction permits for economic facilities, improvements in land allocation mechanisms, optimization of property registration processes, and expanded access to credit resources. These measures have contributed to the creation of new industrial production capacities and an increase in private investment inflows into the industrial sector.

Within Kazakhstan's experience, one of the main directions for enhancing industrial performance lies in the optimal integration of labor and capital resources into the production of goods and services. This resource-efficiency-oriented approach to economic growth aligns with the country's long-term strategic objectives. In particular, Kazakhstan aims to achieve high-income country status by 2050 and to join the group of the world's most developed economies. Achieving this goal requires a substantial improvement in economic efficiency and the formation of an industrial sector capable of producing competitive goods for both domestic and international markets.

Special attention is also being paid to regional development mechanisms as part of Kazakhstan's industrial development strategy. In particular, expanding special and free economic zones, equipping these areas with modern engineering and communication infrastructure, and granting broad permissions for various types of manufacturing activities have been identified as priority tasks. In addition, the introduction of preferential financing mechanisms for establishing new production facilities and reconstructing existing buildings within small industrial zones has further stimulated industrial activity. This practice demonstrates the well-designed regional and institutional nature of Kazakhstan's industrial policy and may be considered a practical experience applicable to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSIONS

The experience of advanced foreign countries analyzed above demonstrates that industrial development requires a comprehensive and long-term approach. By adapting these experiences to the conditions of Uzbekistan, there is significant potential to expand national industry, accelerate structural transformations, and form new production sectors that generate high value added:

First, in developing the industrial sector, a gradual transition from resource-based production to innovation-driven manufacturing based on technological modernization is of critical importance. In this process, the introduction of energy-efficient technologies, the close integration of industry-related service sectors - such as logistics, engineering, and maintenance services - with industrial production, and the expansion of research and development activities within the private sector contribute to the structural development of industry. In addition, developing export-oriented industrial sectors through the production of competitive goods for both domestic and international markets can be considered a key direction based on Germany's experience;

Second, ensuring a stable supply of fuel and energy resources constitutes the material foundation of industrial development. Through the expansion of production capacities, modernization of existing enterprises, and establishment of new industrial facilities, it is possible to achieve quantitative growth of the industrial sector. At the same time, increasing investment in research and development within industrial enterprises and expanding the share of firms with foreign investment participation facilitate the introduction of new technologies and management practices. From the perspective of China's experience, these factors represent important drivers of industrial development;

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Third, the active involvement of the state and the implementation of targeted programs play a decisive role in accelerating industrial development. Through state programs, it is possible to support industrial enterprises, implement special projects in strategic sectors, create new production capacities, and enhance labor productivity, thereby ensuring the expansion of industry. At the same time, orienting industrial development reforms toward the concept of technological sovereignty - namely, strengthening measures aimed at localizing production equipment and key technologies - represents a relevant direction for Uzbekistan, drawing on Russia's experience;

Fourth, the formation of a favorable institutional and economic environment is essential for industrial development. Creating free and competitive conditions for entrepreneurial activity, simplifying land allocation mechanisms for industrial enterprises, and introducing long-term, low-interest financing instruments to attract investment into industry have proven to be effective approaches, as demonstrated by Kazakhstan's experience.

At the same time, international practice indicates that the development of industrial sectors critically depends on the harmonious integration of labor resources, capital, and infrastructure. In this context, expanding special and free economic zones as well as small industrial zones, equipping them with modern engineering and communication infrastructure, enables the creation of new production capacities and accelerates the regional development of industry.

The conducted analysis demonstrates that the experience of developed foreign countries in industrial development is based on a systematic and comprehensive approach. These experiences show that industrial growth can be achieved not only by increasing production volumes, but also through technological modernization, structural diversification, and the expansion of export-oriented manufacturing.

International practice indicates that the development of industrial sectors critically depends on a gradual transition from traditional, resource- and energy-intensive production to innovation-based industries that generate high value added. In this process, strengthening integration between industry and service sectors, promoting research and development with active participation of the private sector, and improving the investment environment emerge as key driving factors.

In addition, targeted state programs and institutional support play an essential role in industrial development. State-led industrial policy creates the necessary conditions for the formation of strategic sectors, the expansion of production capacities, and the achievement of technological sovereignty, thereby contributing to the long-term competitiveness of national industry.

Overall, rather than directly replicating foreign models, adapting international experience to Uzbekistan's specific economic and institutional conditions represents the most effective approach to industrial development. This approach provides a solid scientific and practical foundation for enhancing the effectiveness of national industrial policy and achieving sustainable economic growth.

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